

Calibrating and validating the Aerobic Mortality Risk Index (IRMA): an index for predicting mass mortality of fish due to anoxia.

Fig. 1. Location of the Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta (CGSM), Colombia. Source [4]. Red boxes indicate sampling sites.

Mass mortality of marine organisms are frequent events in estuaries and coastal lagoons, including the Ciénaga Grande de Santa Marta (CGSM), located in the Colombian Caribbean (Fig. 1). The CGSM is considered one of the most productive tropical coastal lagoons in the world [1]. Following a major fish kill in 1994 that resulted in enormous economic losses and serious social impacts, an alert programme for fishermen and environmental authorities was developed.

Considering the increased demand for fish supply during episodes of anoxia and based on a conceptual model explaining the eutrophication process (Fig. 2), Mancera and Vidal developed an index of mortality risk for aerobic organisms called Aerobic Mortality Risk Index (IRMA) [2]. According to the model, rising PO_4 levels stimulate excessive microalgal growth, primarily produced by atmospheric nitrogen-fixing cyanobacteria. Following this overproduction, the cyanobacterial collapse leads to hypoxia or anoxia. Although IRMA was identified as a promising model,

capable of anticipating the 1995 and 1996 mortality events, a lack of sufficient data prevented proper calibration and validation. After nearly 30 years of monitoring by INVEMAR at 33 sites of the CGSM, we resumed the construction of the index.

To estimate IRMA, we improved the algorithms developed by Mancera and

Vidal to score the fish mortality risk based on PO_4 ($\mu\text{mol.L}^{-1}$), chlorophyll (CLA, $\mu\text{g.L}^{-1}$), and dissolved oxygen (OD, mg.L^{-1}) concentrations, using values measured over the past 30 years. We weighted risk scores across the three variables according to their potential impact on fish mortality. The final IRMA value was calculated as the sum of the weighted risk scores (eq. 1), expressed as a percentage:

Where:

n is the number of variables used (3: PO_4 , CLA, OD).

$c(x)$ is the classification of variable x based on its concentration.

$f[c(x)]$ is the weighting applied to each classification.

We calibrated IRMA using fish kill events recorded at CGSM and assessed its efficiency through a confusion matrix, a valuable tool for assessing the performance of statistical models [3]. Before constructing the matrix, we ensured that the sample was balanced, meaning that the number of fish kill events (positive cases) was sufficiently comparable to non-events (negative cases). To achieve this, we used the *upSample* function from the statistical software R. This function performs sampling with replacement to equalize class distributions, ensuring fair representation across both categories (Fig. 3).

Once the sample was balanced, we built the confusion matrix, comparing the predicted classifications of the IRMA index with the actual classifications of fish mortality events. This table summarizes the performance of the

Fig. 2. Conceptual model of the Aerobic Mortality Index (IRMA).

Fig. 3. Diagram of the sample balancing process using the upSampling function from the caret library in R.

Fig. 4. Performance metrics of the Aerobic Mortality Risk Index (IRMA) as a function of different threshold values of the IRMA index.

classification algorithm by providing counts of:

True Positives (TP): Correctly predicted positive cases.

True Negatives (TN): Correctly predicted negative cases.

False Positives (FP): Cases incorrectly predicted as positive (Type I error).

False Negatives (FN): Cases incorrectly predicted as negative (Type II error).

From the values in the confusion matrix, we calculated four key metrics to evaluate the model's performance, including Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and Specificity. These metrics provide

a comprehensive understanding of the IRMA's effectiveness in forecasting fish mortality risks. We then determined a threshold value for the IRMA indicator to optimize assessment metrics, facilitating the distinction between mod-

Table 1. Classification of IRMA fish kills risk levels.

Value (%)	Risk Level
[0,10)	Low
(10,30]	Moderate
(30,40]	High
(40,)	Very high

erate and high-risk levels of fish kill events (Fig. 4). The optimized threshold value was 60%. Finally, we classified the risk levels for the occurrence of fish kill events (Table 1).

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References

1. Cloern JE & AD Jassby 2008. *Ecol Lett* 11:1294–1303. doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2008.01244.x
2. Mancera JE & LA Vidal 1994. *An Inst Invest Mar Punta de Betín* 23:103–117.
3. Tewari K 2022. *Phycology* 2:244–253. doi.org/10.3390/phycolgy2020013.
4. Perdomo Trujillo LV et al 2021. *Estuar Coast Shelf Sci* 248:106888. doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2020.106888.

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